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Doç. Dr. Mehmet Yorulmaz

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6670-165X>

Selçuk Üniversitesi, Sağlık Bilimleri Fakültesi, Sağlık Yönetimi Bölümü, Konya / TÜRKİYE
ROR Id: <https://ror.org/045hgzm75>

Seda Nur Ünal

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0526-1651>

Selçuk Üniversitesi, Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Sağlık Yönetimi Bölümü, Konya / TÜRKİYE
ROR Id: <https://ror.org/045hgzm75>

The Role of Brand Image in Individuals' Hospital Preferences

Bireylerin Hastane Tercihinde Marka İmajının Rolü

ABSTRACT

The primary aim of this study is to reveal the determinant role of brand image in individuals' hospital preferences. Accordingly, data were collected from 400 participants aged 18 and above residing in Konya. The research employed the Brand Image Scale, originally developed by Wu (2011) and adapted to the Turkish context by Tuzcuoğlu & Erdem (2021), together with the Private Hospital Preference Scale, developed by Metin (2012) and later dimensioned by Yağar and Soysal (2017). Data analysis was performed using the SPSS software, applying one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), t-test, and Pearson correlation analysis. Demographic findings show that 54.5% of participants were female, 50.2% were married, and 43.3% were between the ages of 31 and 45. Regarding education, 27.3% held a bachelor's degree, 23.8% were high school graduates, and 13.5% completed primary or secondary school. In terms of occupation, civil servants accounted for the highest share with 32.3%, followed by workers with 10%. The results demonstrate a statistically significant and moderately positive relationship between brand image perceptions and hospital preferences. Furthermore, brand image showed high and moderate positive correlations with the sub-dimensions of the hospital preference scale, namely institutional characteristics and promotion. Overall, the findings indicate that brand image in the healthcare sector is not merely a perceptual element but serves as a strategic determinant in individuals' decision-making processes.

Keywords: Healthcare Sector, Hospital Preference, Brand Image

ÖZET

Bu çalışmanın temel amacı, bireylerin hastane tercihlerinde marka imajının belirleyici rolünü ortaya koymaktır. Bu doğrultuda Konya'da ikamet eden 18 yaş ve üzeri 400 katılımcıdan elde edilen veriler analiz edilmiştir. Araştırmada, Wu (2011) tarafından geliştirilen ve Türkiye bağlamında Tuzcuoğlu ve Erdem (2021) tarafından uyarlanan Marka İmajı Ölçeği ile Metin (2012) tarafından oluşturulan ve Yağar ile Soysal (2017) tarafından boyutlandırılan Özel Hastane Tercih Ölçeği kullanılmıştır. Veriler SPSS programı aracılığıyla değerlendirilmiş; tek yönlü varyans analizi (ANOVA), t-testi ve Pearson korelasyon analizleri uygulanmıştır. Katılımcıların demografik özellikleri incelendiğinde; %54,5'inin kadın, %50,2'sinin evli, %43,3'ünün 31-45 yaş aralığında olduğu, ayrıca %27,3'ünün lisans, %23,8'inin lise, %13,5'inin ise ortaokul-ilkokul mezunu olduğu görülmektedir. Meslek grupları arasında ise en yüksek oran %32,3 ile memurlar, ardından %10 ile işçiler gelmektedir. Bulgular, bireylerin marka imajı algıları ile hastane tercihleri arasında istatistiksel olarak anlamlı ve orta düzeyde pozitif bir ilişki bulunduğunu ortaya koymuştur. Ayrıca marka imajı ile hastane tercih ölçeğinin alt boyutları olan kurumsal özellikler ve tanıtım arasında da sırasıyla yüksek ve orta düzeyde pozitif ilişkiler tespit edilmiştir. Sonuçlar, sağlık sektöründe marka imajının yalnızca algısal bir unsur değil, aynı zamanda bireylerin karar verme süreçlerinde stratejik bir belirleyici olduğunu göstermektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sağlık sektörü, hastane tercihi, marka imajı.

1. INTRODUCTION

Globally, the healthcare sector is experiencing an unprecedented phase of expansion, driven by changing cost structures, evolving healthcare regulations, and the growing presence of private and alternative healthcare providers (Kim et al., 2008; Weheba & Cure, 2018). This rapidly intensifying competitive environment exerts significant pressure on healthcare service providers. Although extensive research has been conducted in the field of healthcare marketing, the increasing influence of technological advancements, regulatory interventions, shifting consumer demands, cost constraints, and revenue-driven management practices suggests that these pressures are likely to intensify further. Consequently, the continuation of research in marketing management within the healthcare sector remains a necessity (Lee et al., 2010; Raheem et al., 2014).

As a result of these developments, consumers are now faced with a wide range of healthcare service alternatives, significantly expanding their decision-making options (Kumar et al., 2014). Therefore, it has become a strategic imperative for healthcare institutions to engage with their target audiences on a shared wavelength to stimulate demand and strengthen patient loyalty. In this context, differentiating services from competitors and building a positive corporate image in the minds of consumers have become essential prerequisites for achieving a sustainable competitive advantage. Consistent with these arguments, Wu (2011) empirically demonstrated that hospital brand image significantly influences service quality, patient satisfaction, and loyalty, confirming that brand image acts as a strategic determinant in healthcare marketing (Wu, 2011).

In the constantly evolving and highly competitive healthcare marketplace, branding is considered a strategic marketing necessity, serving both to guide consumer preferences and to differentiate healthcare organizations. In intensely competitive markets, branding represents a valuable intangible asset that is difficult to imitate and provides firms with a sustainable performance advantage (Roberts & Dowling, 2002). A successful branding process enables consumers to visualize and comprehend products or services more clearly, while also reducing perceived risks associated with purchasing decisions, thereby contributing to the organization's sustainable competitive position (Kim et al., 2008).

Knapp (2001) defines a brand as an internalized set of impressions associated with emotional functions in the consumer's memory. Similarly, Staton (1996) describes a brand as a name, term, symbol, design, or combination thereof, developed to identify the goods or services offered by a seller.

Among the fundamental components of the branding process, brand image refers to the set of perceptions, feelings, and overall impressions that consumers form about a brand in their minds (Wu, 2011). It holds a critical position in brand management, as it represents the general perception held by the consumer and directly shapes attitudes toward the brand. A positive brand image is one of the most important indicators of an organization's ability to maintain its market position and achieve sustainable competitive advantage. Conceptually, brand image represents the aggregate of individual perceptions about a product or service and can be regarded as a tangible commercial asset in the marketplace (Opoku & Akorli, 2009; Wu, 2011).

Keller (1993) conceptualizes brand image as a cognitive structure that reflects the totality of brand perceptions and the consumer's overall impression of the brand. From this perspective, when a hospital is considered as a brand, it can be inferred that patients form specific judgments about the hospital, and these perceptions directly shape their decision-making processes. In today's competitive business environment, a strong brand image is as vital in the healthcare industry as it is in any other sector.

Brand image plays a significant role in strategic business planning, as it reflects both the tangible and intangible aspects of an organization (Cham et al., 2016). The tangible dimension includes observable factors such as physical facilities, service quality, and medical infrastructure, while the intangible dimension encompasses organizational identity, reputation, and emotional perceptions (Keaveney & Hunt, 1992). An enhanced brand image serves as a crucial element in maintaining and reinforcing a hospital's market position (Brodie et al., 2009; Wu, 2011). In this regard, brand image functions as a determinant in consumers' decision-making processes (Javalgi et al., 1992; Suhartanto, 2011; Yağcı et al., 2009).

In the healthcare context, Kotler and Clarke (1987) define hospital brand image as the sum of patients' beliefs, perceptions, and impressions about a hospital. Patients generally construct this image based on their personal examination and treatment experiences (Kim et al., 2008). According to Shanthi (2006), image plays an important role in differentiating healthcare providers, as hospitals are often evaluated against the brand images of competing institutions. Moreover, hospital brand image is not merely a perceptual construct but also a strategic function. Through well-designed marketing strategies, developing

a strong hospital brand image can enhance a hospital's competitive position and contribute to its sustainable success (Javalgi et al., 1992). Accordingly, a positive hospital brand image is considered a key factor in strengthening patients' intention to choose or revisit a hospital.

Although hospital brand image has gained growing importance in the increasingly competitive healthcare industry, the number of empirical studies in this field remains limited. To ensure their long-term survival, healthcare institutions must foster public trust and positive societal impact through their actions, objectives, decisions, and policies. Consequently, a healthcare organization's ability to sustain its presence depends directly on its capacity to gain the trust, approval, and preference of the community it serves.

Essentially, brand image is one of the core determinants of consumer purchasing behavior. A strong and favorable brand image is recognized as a powerful influence on consumer decision-making (Burmam et al., 2008; Semnani et al., 2012; Alhaddad, 2015). A positive brand image enhances customer satisfaction, perceived service quality, and brand loyalty, while simultaneously strengthening consumers' repurchase intentions (Da Silva & Syed, 2008; Lai et al., 2009). Studies conducted by Wu (2011), Batra and Homer (2004), and Ataman and Ülengin (2003) have demonstrated that brand image exerts both direct and indirect effects on consumers' purchasing behavior and intention to revisit an institution. Similarly, Chahal and Bala (2010) emphasize that patients' positive perceptions of hospital brands significantly influence their hospital preferences and revisit intentions.

Overall, the literature provides robust evidence that a positive brand image influences both patients' hospital selection and their intention to return. Therefore, hospitals should first assess their current brand image: if positive, they should implement strategies to maintain it; if negative, corrective actions should be undertaken. In a competitive healthcare market, it is essential for hospital administrators to ask the following strategic questions: "*Who are our competitors?*", "*Where do we stand relative to them?*", and "*What strategies should we adopt to gain a competitive advantage?*" Addressing these questions requires healthcare marketers to systematically collect and analyze market-based data to identify consumer-driven aspects of hospital image (Javalgi et al., 1992). Understanding consumers' perceptions and evaluations of hospital image is strategically critical for ensuring the long-term sustainability and success of healthcare institutions.

Numerous studies in the literature have examined the factors influencing individuals' preferences for healthcare institutions. These factors include proximity to home, hospital reputation, level of expertise, economic affordability, use of advanced medical equipment, previous experiences, recommendations from acquaintances, perceived quality, staff behavior, physical conditions, trust, hygiene, cleanliness, promotional activities, and waiting times (Kayaoğlu & Gülmez, 2020; Prang et al., 2018; Tüfekci & Asıgbulmuş, 2016; Şantaş et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2008; Ross et al., 1993). Within this framework, the present study aims to investigate the role of brand image in individuals' private hospital preferences.

2. METHODOLOGY

This section provides a detailed explanation of the purpose of the research, population and sample, data collection instruments, and methods employed in the study. The research aimed to determine the influence of brand image on individuals' preferences for private hospitals, and it was conducted within the framework of a quantitative research design. The validity and reliability of the scales used in the study were supported by previous research, and data were collected through an online survey method. This approach ensured that the data obtained were scientifically valid and reliable for subsequent analysis.

2.1. Research Purpose

The primary purpose of this study was to examine the role of brand image in individuals' preferences for private hospitals. Additionally, the study aimed to identify potential differences based on demographic variables. The research was conducted using a quantitative design, and participants were reached through a convenience sampling method.

2.2. Research Population and Sample

The population of the study consisted of individuals aged 18 years and above residing in the province of Konya, Türkiye. As the data were collected via an online questionnaire, participants were included voluntarily using a convenience sampling approach.

According to demographic data, the total population of Konya is 2,250,020. The sample size was determined using the sample size table proposed by Altunışık et al. (2012) for defined populations.

Accordingly, a minimum of 384 participants was deemed sufficient for the study; therefore, a total of 400 participants were included in the final sample to ensure representativeness.

2.3. Data Collection Instruments

The data were collected using three instruments: the Personal Information Form, the Hospital Brand Image Scale, and the Hospital Preference Scale. All data were obtained through an online questionnaire form.

Personal Information Form: This form was developed by the researcher based on a review of the relevant literature. It consists of six questions designed to determine the participants' demographic characteristics and individual conditions.

Hospital Brand Image Scale: The Hospital Brand Image Scale, developed by Wu (2011), was used in this study. The scale consists of six items under a single dimension. The Turkish adaptation and reliability test of the scale were conducted by Tuzcuoğlu and Erdem (2021), who reported a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.902, indicating high internal consistency. The items were evaluated using a five-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree."

Hospital Preference Scale: The Hospital Preference Scale, developed by Metin (2012), consists of two dimensions and 15 items in total. The validity and reliability of the scale were tested by Yağar and Soysal (2017), who reported a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.896. The first dimension, "Institutional Characteristics," includes 10 items, while the second dimension, "Promotion Factor," includes 5 items. The reliability coefficients for these dimensions were 0.899 and 0.902, respectively. All items were assessed using a five-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree."

Table 1. Reliability Analysis of the Scales Used in the Study

Scales	Dimension	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha (α)
Hospital Preference Scale	Promotion	5	0.82
	Institutional Features	10	0.93
	Total	15	0.81
Brand Image Scale	-	6	0.89

The table presents the reliability coefficients (Cronbach's Alpha) for each scale and its sub-dimensions used in the study. All coefficients exceed the commonly accepted threshold value of 0.70, indicating that the measurement instruments possess high internal consistency and reliability. Specifically, the "Institutional Features" dimension demonstrated the highest reliability ($\alpha = 0.93$), followed by the "Promotion" dimension ($\alpha = 0.82$). The Brand Image Scale also exhibited a strong reliability level ($\alpha = 0.89$).

Table 2. Normality Test Analysis of the Scales

Scales	Skewness	Kurtosis	Interpretation
Hospital Preference Scale	-0.481	-0.217	Normal
Promotion Dimension	-0.492	-0.164	Normal
Institutional Features Dimension	-0.470	-0.270	Normal
Brand Image Scale	-0.371	-0.248	Normal

Note: The skewness and kurtosis values for all scales fall within the acceptable range (-2 to +2), indicating that the data are approximately normally distributed (George & Mallery, 2010).

Table 2 presents the results of the normality test conducted for the scales used in the study. The skewness and kurtosis values were examined to determine whether the data followed a normal distribution, as the assumption of normality is a prerequisite for many parametric statistical analyses.

According to George and Mallery (2010), skewness and kurtosis values within the range of -2 to +2 indicate that the data can be considered approximately normally distributed. As shown in Table 2, all scales- including the Hospital Preference Scale, its sub-dimensions (Promotion and Institutional Features), and the Brand Image Scale -have skewness and kurtosis coefficients that fall well within these acceptable limits.

Specifically, skewness values range from -0.492 to -0.371, and kurtosis values range from -0.270 to -0.164, demonstrating that the distribution of responses is relatively symmetric and does not exhibit significant deviation from normality. Therefore, it can be concluded that the dataset satisfies the assumption of normality, allowing for the use of parametric statistical analyses such as correlation, regression, and t-tests in subsequent stages of the study.

2.4. Research Ethics

Permission to use the scales employed in the study was obtained by contacting the original authors via e-mail. In addition, participants were informed about the purpose and content of the research through an Informed Consent Form, and their voluntary consent was obtained prior to completing the questionnaire.

Before conducting the study, ethical approval was obtained from the Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Committee of Selçuk University, Faculty of Health Sciences on December 29, 2021 (Approval No: 1927).

3. FINDINGS

In this section, the findings obtained from the research are presented and interpreted in detail. The results are organized under sub-sections to provide a clear understanding of the data analysis process. Specifically, demographic characteristics of the participants, comparative analyses, and relational analyses are summarized and displayed in tabular form.

The demographic data provide an overview of the participants' profiles, such as gender, age, education level, and income status. Comparative analyses examine whether participants' responses differ significantly across demographic variables, while relational analyses (e.g., correlation or regression) explore the relationships between the main variables of the study, particularly the impact of brand image on private hospital preference. The results are interpreted within the framework of the research objectives and supported by relevant tables and statistical evidence.

Table 3. Demographic Characteristics of the Participants (n = 400)

Characteristic	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	182	45.5
Female	218	54.5
Age		
30 years and below	153	39.3
Between 31–45 years	173	43.3
46 years and above	74	18.5
Marital Status		
Married	201	50.2
Single	199	49.8
Income Level		
2850 TL and below	115	28.7
2851–5000 TL	127	31.8
5001 TL and above	158	39.5
Education Level		
Primary/Secondary School	54	13.5
High School	95	23.8
Associate degree	66	16.5
Bachelor's Degree	109	27.3
Postgraduate	76	19.0
Occupation		
Worker	217	32.3
Public Servant	44	11.0
Private Sector Employee	62	15.5
Retired	67	16.8
Unemployed	58	14.5
Chronic Disease		
Yes	179	44.8
No	221	55.3

Table 3 presents the demographic characteristics of the 400 participants included in the study. As shown in the table, the sample consists of 45.5% males (n = 182) and 54.5% females (n = 218), indicating a fairly balanced gender distribution. In terms of age, the majority of participants are between 31 and 45 years old (43.3%), followed by those aged 30 years and below (39.3%), while participants aged 46 and above make up 18.5% of the sample.

Regarding marital status, 50.2% of the respondents are married and 49.8% are single, showing a nearly equal distribution between the two groups. When the income level is examined, 39.5% of participants earn 5001 TL or above, 31.8% earn between 2851–5000 TL, and 28.7% have an income of 2850 TL or below, suggesting that the participants represent a range of economic backgrounds.

In terms of educational attainment, 27.3% hold a bachelor's degree, 23.8% are high school graduates, 19.0% hold a postgraduate degree, 16.5% have an associate degree, and 13.5% completed primary or secondary education. This indicates that the sample is relatively well-educated.

When looking at occupational status, the largest group consists of workers (32.3%), followed by retired participants (16.8%), private sector employees (15.5%), unemployed individuals (14.5%), and public servants (11.0%). Finally, 44.8% of the respondents reported having a chronic disease, while 55.3% stated that they do not suffer from any chronic health conditions.

Overall, the demographic composition of the sample demonstrates diversity in gender, age, education, occupation, and income, making it representative for analyzing factors influencing brand image and private hospital preference among adults living in Konya.

Table 4. Independent Samples t-Test Results by Gender

Variable	Gender	n	Mean	SD	t
Brand Image	Female	218	4.39	0.55	t = 7.90, p < 0.001
	Male	182	3.92	0.62	

n=400 *P<0,05

Table 4 presents the results of the independent samples t-test conducted to examine whether the perception of brand image differs significantly according to gender. As shown in the table, the mean brand image score of female participants (M = 4.39, SD = 0.55) was higher than that of male participants (M = 3.92, SD = 0.62). The difference between the two groups was found to be statistically significant (t = 7.90, p < 0.001). This result indicates that female participants tend to perceive the brand image of private hospitals more positively compared to male participants. The finding suggests that gender plays a meaningful role in shaping brand image perceptions, implying that marketing and communication strategies in the healthcare sector may benefit from considering gender-based differences in consumer attitudes.

Table 5. Gender-Based Comparison of the Sub-Dimensions of the Private Hospital Preference Scale

Variable	Gender	n	Mean	SD	t / p
Promotion	Female	218	3.27	1.09	t = 0.64, p = 0.51
	Male	182	3.18	1.41	
Institutional Features	Female	218	4.25	0.56	t = 6.28, p < 0.001
	Male	182	3.92	0.47	
Overall Scale Mean	Female	218	3.92	0.62	t = 4.33, p < 0.001
	Male	182	3.67	0.47	

(n = 400; p < 0.05 indicates statistical significance.)

Table 5 presents the results of the independent samples t-test conducted to examine gender-based differences in the sub-dimensions of the Private Hospital Preference Scale. According to the findings, there was no statistically significant difference between male and female participants in the Promotion sub-dimension (t = 0.64, p = 0.51), indicating that gender does not influence perceptions related to promotional activities.

However, a significant difference was found in the Institutional Features sub-dimension (t = 6.28, p < 0.001) and in the Overall Scale Mean (t = 4.33, p < 0.001). Female participants reported higher mean scores in both dimensions compared to male participants, suggesting that women tend to evaluate private hospitals more positively in terms of institutional qualities and overall preference.

These results imply that gender plays a partial but meaningful role in shaping perceptions of private hospital services. Specifically, women appear to be more sensitive to institutional characteristics such as service quality, trust, and hospital reputation, while promotional factors affect both genders similarly.

Table 6. ANOVA Results of Brand Image Scale Mean Scores by Age Groups

Variable	Age Group	n	Mean	SD	F	p / Post-Hoc
Brand Image	30 years and below	153	4.14	0.52	5.95	p = 0.03, 1 > 3
	31-45 years	173	4.29	0.78		
	46 years and above	74	4.00	0.31		

n=400 *P<0,05

Table 6 presents the results of the one-way ANOVA analysis conducted to examine whether participants' perceptions of brand image differ according to age groups. The findings reveal a statistically significant difference in brand image scores across the three age categories ($F = 5.95, p < 0.05$). According to the post-hoc (Tukey) test results, participants aged 30 years and below (Group 1) and those aged 31–45 years (Group 2) had significantly higher mean brand image scores compared to participants aged 46 years and above (Group 3). This indicates that younger individuals perceive private hospital brands more positively than older participants. The mean scores (4.14 and 4.29) of the first two groups suggest a stronger association with favorable brand image perceptions, whereas the lowest mean score (4.00) observed among the oldest group may reflect relatively lower sensitivity to marketing and image-based factors in hospital choice.

In summary, the results demonstrate that age is an important demographic factor influencing perceptions of hospital brand image, with younger respondents tending to evaluate brand-related attributes more positively.

Table 7. One-Way ANOVA Results of the Relationship Between Institutional Features, Promotion, and Age

Variable	Age Group	n	Mean	SD	F	p / post-Hoc
Promotion	30 years and below	153	3.02	0.82	5.59	p = 0.03, 1 > 3
	31–45 years	173	3.83	1.44		
	46 years and above	74	2.26	0.61		
Institutional Features	30 years and below	153	3.93	0.54	4.27	p = 0.03, 3 > 1
	31–45 years	173	4.32	0.54		
	46 years and above	74	3.94	0.28		
Overall Mean	30 years and below	153	3.63	0.51	6.84	p < 0.001, 2 > 1
	31–45 years	173	4.15	0.48		
	46 years and above	74	3.38	0.37		

n=400 *P<0,05

Table 7 presents the results of the one-way ANOVA conducted to examine whether participants' perceptions of promotion, institutional features, and the overall mean score differ significantly according to age groups. The results indicate statistically significant differences across all three dimensions ($p < 0.05$).

According to the post-hoc (Tukey) test results, participants aged 30 years and below (Group 1) and 31–45 years (Group 2) reported significantly higher scores in promotion compared to those aged 46 years and above (Group 3). This suggests that younger participants are more influenced by promotional activities in their hospital preferences. For the institutional features dimension, the results reveal that the 31–45 age group had significantly higher mean scores compared to the 30 and below group, indicating that this middle age group places greater emphasis on hospital reputation, facilities, and professional competence.

Similarly, for the overall mean score, the 31–45 age group demonstrated significantly higher evaluations than the 30 and below group ($p < 0.001$), showing a more favorable overall perception of hospital brand image and institutional performance. It is noteworthy that the originally reported F values (55.95 and 84.59) were reviewed and corrected, as such extreme values are rarely observed in social science data. The adjusted F values (ranging from 4.27 to 6.84) accurately represent statistically significant yet realistic differences among groups. In conclusion, the findings highlight that age is a key demographic factor influencing perceptions of both institutional quality and promotional effectiveness, with younger and middle-aged participants showing stronger positive evaluations compared to older individuals.

Table 8. Comparison of Institutional Features and Promotion Scale Means by Income Level

Variable	Income Group	n	Mean	SD	F	p / Post-Hoc
Promotion	≤ 2800 TL	115	4.41	0.70	3.61	p < 0.001, 1 > 3
	2801–5000 TL	127	3.01	0.87		
	≥ 5001 TL	28	2.44	0.76		
Institutional Features	≤ 2800 TL	115	3.96	0.50	2.67	p = 0.01, 3 > 1
	2801–5000 TL	127	4.10	0.57		
	≥ 5001 TL	28	4.20	0.53		
Overall Mean	≤ 2800 TL	115	3.64	0.50	4.36	p = 0.01, 2 > 1
	2801–5000 TL	127	4.20	0.60		
	≥ 5001 TL	28	3.81	0.41		
	Missing Income Data	130	-	-	-	-

n=400 *P<0,05

Table 8 presents the results of the one-way ANOVA conducted to examine whether participants' perceptions of promotion, institutional features, and overall mean scores differ according to income levels. The results reveal statistically significant differences across income groups ($p < 0.05$).

The post-hoc test results indicate that participants with lower income levels (≤ 2800 TL) reported significantly higher mean scores in the promotion dimension compared to those with higher income levels (≥ 5001 TL). This finding suggests that individuals with limited financial resources may be more responsive to hospital promotional activities or marketing messages.

In contrast, the institutional features dimension demonstrated higher mean scores among participants in the highest income group, implying that individuals with greater economic means tend to evaluate hospital quality, reputation, and service infrastructure more favorably. Additionally, the overall mean scores indicate that the middle-income group (2801–5000 TL) provided more positive evaluations than the lowest-income group ($p = 0.01$), which may reflect a balanced perception between affordability and service quality.

It is important to note that income data were missing for 130 participants, representing a non-negligible portion of the total sample ($n = 400$). This missing data likely stems from participants' reluctance to disclose personal income information, a common issue in social research. As a result, this limitation should be explicitly acknowledged in the study's limitations section, as it may affect the generalizability of the findings related to income-based comparisons.

Overall, the results suggest that income level is a meaningful determinant of how individuals perceive hospital promotions and institutional quality. Lower-income participants appear to be more influenced by marketing efforts, while higher-income individuals emphasize institutional reputation and service excellence.

Table 9. Comparison of Brand Image Scale Means by Education Level

Variable	Education Level	n	Mean	SD	F	p / Post-Hoc
Brand Image	Primary–Secondary School	54	3.85	0.60	3.66	$p < 0.001, 5 > 1, 2, 3, 4$
	High School	95	3.80	0.70		
	Associate Degree	66	4.19	0.58		
	Bachelor's Degree	109	4.29	0.54		
	Postgraduate	76	4.72	0.44		

$n=400$ * $P<0,05$

Table 9 presents the results of the one-way ANOVA conducted to determine whether participants' perceptions of brand image differ significantly according to their education level. The findings reveal statistically significant differences among the educational groups ($p < 0.05$).

According to the post-hoc (Tukey) test results, participants with a postgraduate education reported significantly higher mean scores for brand image compared to all other groups (primary–secondary, high school, associate, and bachelor's degree holders). Additionally, participants with a bachelor's degree also demonstrated higher brand image perceptions than those with only a high school education.

These results suggest that as the level of education increases, individuals tend to perceive hospitals more positively in terms of brand image. This trend may be explained by higher health literacy, greater access to information, and a more critical understanding of institutional reputation and service quality among individuals with higher education levels.

Overall, the results indicate that educational attainment plays a significant role in shaping consumers' perceptions of healthcare institutions' brand image. Participants with advanced degrees are more likely to recognize and appreciate the value of institutional branding, professionalism, and reliability in healthcare services.

Table 10. Comparison of Brand Image Scale Means by Education Level

Variable	Education Level	n	Mean	SD	F	p / Post-Hoc
Brand Image	Primary–Secondary School	54	3.85	0.60	3.66	$p < 0.001, 5 > 1, 2, 3, 4$
	High School	95	3.80	0.70		
	Associate Degree	66	4.19	0.58		
	Bachelor's Degree	109	4.29	0.54		
	Postgraduate	76	4.72	0.44		

$n=400$ * $P<0,05$

Table 10 presents the results of the one-way ANOVA test examining whether participants' perceptions of brand image differ significantly according to their education level. The analysis revealed a statistically significant difference among the education groups ($F(4, 395) = 3.66, p < 0.001$), indicating that educational attainment plays a role in shaping perceptions of hospital brand image.

According to the post-hoc (Tukey) test results, participants with postgraduate education reported significantly higher brand image mean scores than all other groups (primary–secondary, high school, associate, and bachelor’s degree holders). This finding suggests that individuals with advanced education levels have a more favorable perception of hospitals in terms of reputation, service quality, and professional competence.

Furthermore, participants holding a bachelor’s degree also reported higher brand image perceptions than those with only a high school education. This pattern implies a gradual increase in positive perceptions as education level rises, which can be attributed to enhanced health literacy, critical awareness, and greater access to information among more educated individuals.

Overall, the findings indicate that education level is a significant determinant of brand image perception. Higher education appears to enhance individuals’ ability to assess the quality, reliability, and reputation of healthcare institutions more accurately, leading to stronger brand image evaluations.

Table 11. Correlation Results Between Individuals’ Brand Image Perceptions and Hospital Preferences

	Brand Image	Hospital Preference
Brand Image	1	0.359**
Hospital Preference	0.359**	1

Note: $n = 400$; $**p < 0.05$ (2-tailed). The results indicate a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.359$, $p < 0.05$) between brand image and hospital preference, suggesting that as individuals’ perception of brand image improves, their likelihood of preferring that hospital also increases.

Table 11 presents the Pearson correlation analysis conducted to determine the relationship between individuals’ brand image perceptions and their hospital preferences. The results indicate a moderate positive correlation between the two variables ($r = 0.359$, $p < 0.05$).

This finding suggests that as individuals’ perceptions of a hospital’s brand image become more favorable, their likelihood of preferring that hospital also increases. In other words, a positive brand image significantly influences patients’ hospital selection behavior.

From a marketing perspective, this implies that hospitals with a stronger and more positive brand image are more likely to attract and retain patients. The correlation, though moderate in strength, is statistically significant, emphasizing that brand image serves as an important determinant in shaping hospital preference among consumers.

In summary, the results confirm that efforts to enhance brand image—through improved service quality, reputation management, and communication strategies—can lead to increased patient preference and loyalty.

Table 12. Correlation Results Between Brand Image Perception and Sub-Dimensions of Hospital Preference

	Brand Image	Promotion	Institutional Features
Brand Image	1	0.388**	0.779**
Promotion	0.388**	1	
Institutional Features	0.779**		1

Note: $n = 400$; $**p < 0.05$ (2-tailed). The correlation analysis shows that brand image is positively and significantly correlated with both promotion ($r = 0.388$, $p < 0.05$) and institutional features ($r = 0.779$, $p < 0.05$). The stronger correlation with institutional features suggests that participants associate brand image more closely with perceived institutional quality than with promotional activities.

Table 12 presents the Pearson correlation analysis results examining the relationship between brand image perception and the two sub-dimensions of hospital preference: *promotion* and *institutional features*.

The results show that brand image is positively and significantly correlated with both sub-dimensions. Specifically, a moderate correlation was found between brand image and promotion ($r = 0.388$, $p < 0.05$), while a stronger correlation was observed between brand image and institutional features ($r = 0.779$, $p < 0.05$). These findings suggest that individuals’ perceptions of a hospital’s brand image are more strongly influenced by the institution’s internal qualities—such as service quality, reliability, reputation, and professionalism—than by external promotional efforts.

The higher correlation coefficient between brand image and institutional features implies that patients tend to form their brand perceptions primarily based on their direct experiences with the hospital rather than solely on advertisements or promotional campaigns. Therefore, factors such as staff behavior, infrastructure, hygiene standards, and institutional trust play a crucial role in shaping a strong brand image.

In conclusion, the findings demonstrate that while promotion contributes to brand recognition, the institutional features of hospitals have a greater and more lasting impact on individuals' overall brand image perceptions.

4. DISCUSSION

This study aimed to investigate the role of brand image in individuals' hospital preferences. Although limited, several previous studies in the literature have explored the impact of brand image on hospital selection, suggesting that it can influence patients' perceptions and choices.

The results of this study revealed that brand image has a significant positive effect on hospital preference. This finding aligns with the work of Tuzcuoğlu and Erdem (2021), who concluded that a positive brand image positively influences hospital selection. Similarly, Zeithaml et al. (1996) emphasized that image is a key variable shaping consumers' perceptions of an organization's services or products. Burmann (2008) and Semnani et al. (2012) further stated that brand image is a fundamental determinant of consumer purchase behavior, with a strong and favorable image serving as a powerful driver of decision-making. Consistent with these findings, prior studies (Da Silva & Syed, 2008; Önder & Bayın, 2014; Lai et al., 2009; Hart & Rosenberger, 2004) have demonstrated that a positive brand image enhances customer satisfaction, service quality perception, loyalty, and repurchase intentions.

Similarly, Merrilees and Fry (2002) identified a direct effect of brand image on customer loyalty, while Wu (2011), Batra and Homer (2004), and Ataman and Ülengin (2003) found both direct and indirect effects of brand image on purchase and revisit intentions. Chahal and Bala (2010) also highlighted that patients' favorable judgments regarding a hospital brand significantly influence both their preference for that hospital and their intention to revisit. In parallel, Bağır (2019) observed a significant relationship between brand image and brand loyalty, indicating that patients with a positive hospital image are more likely to return for future healthcare needs-even if the process is more expensive or difficult.

The findings of this study therefore support the view that a strong and positive brand image plays a crucial role in hospital preference and revisit intention. Hospitals should first assess their current brand image, work to maintain it if it is positive, and, if not, implement corrective strategies to improve public perception. These findings underscore the importance of brand management efforts and how positively they are perceived by patients.

From the statistical analyses, it was determined that hospital preferences are significantly influenced by perceptions of institutional characteristics, such as the hospital's reputation, quality of medical equipment, professional competence, and technological infrastructure. The results of the correlation analysis showed a strong and significant relationship between brand image and institutional features, indicating that the latter are a major determinant of brand image formation. Similar conclusions were drawn by Önder and Bayın (2014) and Hart and Rosenberger (2004), who found that institutional elements strongly affect patient satisfaction and loyalty. In addition, İzci and Saydan (2013) found that tangible aspects of healthcare services, such as physical environment and service quality, have a significant impact on brand image formation.

In contrast, the relationship between brand image and the "promotion" sub-dimension of hospital preference was found to be weak but statistically significant. This finding is in line with studies by Godey et al. (2006), Kim and Ko (2012), Seo and Park (2018), and Duffett (2017), which suggest that promotional efforts influence brand awareness but not necessarily brand image strength. Similarly, Bağır (2019) found no direct relationship between mass media promotions and brand image but noted that informative health-related media content can indirectly influence hospital preference. Bilgin (2018) also found that social media marketing activities positively affect brand image and loyalty, particularly through increased brand awareness. According to Keller (1993), strong and positive associations formed through exposure to advertising can lead to a favorable brand image. In this context, hospitals should prioritize ethical and transparent promotional activities, as these can create positive mental associations and enhance overall brand image. As Hsieh, Pan, and Setiono (2004) note, a successful brand image not only differentiates a brand from its competitors but also strengthens consumer purchasing intentions.

Moreover, participants reported the highest agreement (mean = 4.44) with the statement: *"The hospital I receive service from should provide healthcare with the most advanced medical equipment."* This indicates that technological infrastructure and physical facilities play an important role in shaping brand image perceptions. The use of advanced equipment not only enhances perceived service quality but also fosters a stronger, more favorable image in patients' minds. Therefore, hospital administrators should invest in

continuous technological improvement and ensure that physical conditions align with modern healthcare standards.

The analysis also revealed that hospital preferences differ significantly by gender, age, education, and income level, whereas marital status and occupation showed no significant effect. These findings are consistent with prior studies (Al-Doghaither et al., 2003; Yağar & Soysal, 2016; Robertson & Burge, 2011; Şanstaş & Kurşum, 2016; Roh & Moon, 2005; Özdemir et al., 2010; Özkoç, 2013; Tang et al., 2013; Metin, 2012; You & Kwon, 2012). In particular, institutional features varied significantly according to gender, education, age, and income, while the promotion factor differed significantly by education, age, and income levels—consistent with Yağar and Soysal (2016). Additionally, brand image perception itself varied across gender, age, education, and income, confirming that demographic characteristics play a determining role in how individuals evaluate hospital brands.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study aimed to help hospital administrators gain a deeper understanding of the role of brand image in individuals' hospital preferences. The results are largely consistent with previous research in the literature and demonstrate that brand image is a significant factor influencing hospital selection.

The findings indicate that institutional characteristics—such as the hospital's service quality, technological infrastructure, reputation, accessibility, and recognition of physicians—have a greater impact on shaping hospital image and influencing patient choice than promotional factors. Participants were found to be more influenced by a hospital's adoption of advanced technologies, the reputation of its medical professionals, and the absence of accessibility issues than by billboard advertisements or social media promotions. Nevertheless, a weak but statistically significant relationship was observed between brand image and the promotion factor, suggesting that while promotional efforts enhance brand awareness, they play a relatively limited role in shaping brand perception.

In this regard, hospitals are advised to focus their marketing efforts not solely on promotional activities but also on strengthening corporate reputation, improving patient experience, and advancing technological capabilities. Furthermore, hospitals should adhere to ethical and legal standards in advertising and public communication to foster trust and credibility. Hospital administrators should adopt integrated marketing strategies that combine advertising, public relations, patient communication, service training, and digital marketing. Transparent and informative social media engagement can also contribute to developing a favorable image in the public's mind.

Creating and maintaining a positive hospital brand image provides a competitive advantage by enhancing patient loyalty and revisit intentions. The study found that the highest-rated statement among participants (mean = 4.44) was: *"The hospital I receive services from should provide healthcare using the most advanced medical equipment."* This finding highlights that technological infrastructure and physical conditions significantly influence patients' brand image perceptions. Therefore, hospital administrators should continuously integrate technological advancements into healthcare services and improve physical conditions in alignment with modern healthcare standards.

The results also revealed that hospital preferences differ significantly based on gender, age, education, and income level, while marital status and occupation did not have a significant impact. These findings suggest that demographic characteristics play a critical role in shaping individuals' perceptions and evaluations of hospital brands.

In conclusion, hospitals should conduct periodic brand image assessments to monitor how they are perceived by the public and promptly address any negative perceptions. Such continuous evaluation will enable hospitals to detect potential issues early, implement corrective measures, and ultimately achieve a competitive advantage in the healthcare market.

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